

Women’s Entrepreneurship Creative Strategy for Improving Eco Business

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Abstract:- The women’s role in the entrepreneur environment is increased by the time. The trade sector is the place which many women entrepreneur chose with 49.5%. Creative business is growing in the trade sector and from 1633 women correspondent, 809 women entrepreneurs is doing creative business such as craft and fashion. Meanwhile, women’s creativity is underestimated by the previous studies. The studies said that women are less creative than men. Fortunately, women holding high value due to their feminine nature in environmental issues that can help them to build the business.

Eco business become the concern according to the women strength value in entrepreneurship. The benchmarking to the brand is important to learn more about the strength and weaknesses. The women-owned brand in eco business is analyzed using Resource Based View and Value, Rarity, Imitation, and Organization (VRIO) as the internal analysis tools and the external analysis tools is using PESTLE and Porter Five Forces. The exploration of business problem is the root of the research objectives for finding creatives strategies that are suitable for eco business.

In this research, the author also using in-depth interview as the data collection tools in the qualitative methodology to know the competitor analysis. The process involves three brands, two brands’ women-owned entrepreneurs and one brand male-owned entrepreneurs.

The interview resulted that the women entrepreneurs lacking of developing the eco product because they are weak in creating branding content and increasing product value. Then they also had fewer interactions with customers and currently the women’s have obstacles in learning creative strategies because many barriers they encounter.

The conclusion of the research found that the creative strategy proposed are branding 101 and new product development. The women entrepreneurs are no less creative than men in implementing creative strategy. The implementation plan guide is the action plan and the tool for monitoring the strategy is the time schedule. This study is to solve the women entrepreneur’s problems in creative business and to grow their businesses.

Keywords:- branding 101, creative strategy, eco product, new product development, PESTLE, Porter Five Forces, VRIO, women entrepreneurship.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor in 2014, Indonesian women ranks in the second percentages by 36% among selected countries Malaysia, Philippines, China, and India. The gap percentages between male and female in Indonesia are low and the prevalence rate has high overall – see Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Entrepreneurship Prevalence Rates by Gender in Indonesia and Selected Countries by Global Entrepreneurship Monitor in 2014

(Source: The World Bank, 2016)

From the Figure 1. shown that the women entrepreneurs' creativity is important for the country in the global entrepreneurship rate. Thus, the business sector where women growing their business should be supported by the government. The women entrepreneur deployment in Indonesia's business sectors is reported in the Table 1. From 1633 women entrepreneurs in Indonesia, the most common business sector they led is in trade (49.5%). The second sector is manufacturing sector (24.3%). The number of

businesses were quite high is written with the red color. The business sector of trade is the top higher of percentages chosen by women if compared with other sectors. Those two sectors are where the most creative business existed such as fashion and craft. However, there is still an obstacle for women to be a creative entrepreneur, women are not better than men in masculine traits of being more adventurousness and self-reliance.

What is the sector of your main business? (N=1633)			
No.	Business Sector	Freq	Percent
03.	Plantation	1	0.1%
08.	Manufacturing	396	24.3%
10.	Building/Construction	1	0.1%
11.	Trade	809	49.5%
12.	Hotel & Restaurant	218	13.4%
13.	Transportation and Warehousing	2	0.1%
16.	Education Services	10	0.6%
17.	Health Services	9	0.6%
18.	Governmental and individual social services	185	11.3%
95.	Others (massage service & makeup service)	2	0.1%
Total		1,633	100%

Table 1: Business Sectors of Women Entrepreneurs in Indonesia.

(Source: Women Entrepreneurs in Indonesia: A Pathway to Increasing Shared Prosperity by The World Bank, 2016)

The creative business in Indonesia having many issues such as the product development and product branding. The women's creativity is arguable to take responsibilities to resolve the issue because the research studies resulted that creativity is strongly associated with stereotypically masculine-agentic qualities and both experimental and archival data indicated that men are judged as more creative than women (Proudfoot et al., 2015). Thus, the research questions are as follow:

- What is the creative strategy for women entrepreneur to improve the eco business in Indonesia?
- How the creative strategy leads the women entrepreneur in the eco business?
- How the eco product development implemented the strategy for?

The answer will be the guidance for the women entrepreneurs to build their business. To support women entrepreneurs, this paper will provide some tools to help the women-owned brand in eco business adjust their strategy and dress the part to be successful brand.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This part is defining the "why" of the factors appeared from author's thoughts, reviews, and summaries about the business literature. There are several points to review that are women entrepreneurship in Indonesia, women entrepreneur's creativity, and women's creativity for eco business.

A. Women entrepreneurship in Indonesia

Women entrepreneurs are women participating in the total entrepreneurial activity, able to deal with risks, and able to identify opportunities in their environment to combine resources in a unique way so as to take the advantage of business they do (Anggadwita & Dhewanto, 2015). Women entrepreneurs in Indonesia is developing in many sectors. At the age of 78 years old Indonesia as an independence country, the Indonesian women movement and innovation is never diminished. As evidenced by the increasing number of professional spaces for Indonesian women, the latest data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) showed Indonesian women's employment rate at 39.19 percent in 2019 like Global Entrepreneurship Monitor report. Women-owned Small Medium Enterprises (WSME) has a different definition across countries, simply describe as an enterprise which 'owned' by a woman. It can be owned by a single individual or a group of individuals. In the Figure 2 showing the estimation data of WSMEs population in Indonesia in 2015.

Fig. 2: Estimated population of WSMEs in Indonesia (2015)

(Source: Women and Entrepreneurship Indonesia, Sydney Southeast Asia Centre, The University of Sydney, 2017)

From the diagram of total population, the participation of women in business (11.6%) was smaller than the participation rate of men (22.1%). The gap between unemployed + other¹ female and male is small from 88.4% for female and 77.9% for male but the number of males in workforce is higher than female. From 127.9M women in Indonesia, only 5.5M people who become employer while men already at 17.3M people. It means that women’s participation is lower than men in economic activity of this country and that makes women be the most vulnerable economic participants.

B. Women Entrepreneur’s Creativity

Women have started to build the ability to run a business. This is necessary so that women began to be compared to the ranks of men (Hani et al., 2012). Women who decided to be an entrepreneur have shifted some certain mindset. These mindsets are tools for someone to be a successful business owner which are resilience, confidence, attitude towards finances, ability to deal with failure, innovate and stick with their business for the long haul. Unfortunately, women often have more doubt and insecurity about their abilities and talents-insecurities that can hold them back from ever starting down the entrepreneurial path (Kay and Shipman, 2014). Women also argued as an empathetic, emotional, and more compassionate human being due to their feminine competencies, they judged better suited to employ inclusive strategies and lead social enterprises rather than men. While in another research result, to think creatively tends to be associated with independence and self-direction, qualities generally ascribed to men, so that men are often perceived to be more creative than women (Proudfoot et al., 2015).

C. Women and Eco Business

The growth of women entrepreneurs in Indonesia is significantly high but the women who handling their business with eco value is still rare. Focusing on the value of the product is one of the part entrepreneurial opportunities. To have entrepreneurship, you must first have entrepreneurial opportunities (Shane. S. & Venkataram S, 2012).

Entrepreneurial opportunities are those situations in which new goods, services, raw materials, and organizing methods can be introduced at greater than their cost of production (Casson, 1982). The branding is easier to introduced to the market if the brand builds a strong value. Indonesian women entrepreneurs should create that strong value and take those opportunities and lead the company confidently.

Eco business is a regularly said as a business which use green values as their core values, implement green actions such as selling organic products and recycling waste, and pay attention to the sustainability of the environment (Gunawan & Dhewanto, 2012). That is also the reason why eco business always referred to as green business. Deputy of Natural Resources-Environment, Ministry of National Development Planning/BAPPENAS, reported that there are four concepts of green business in Indonesia, which are biodegradable, minimum waste, efficient use of resources because its non-renewable, continuously available or does not produce waste that cannot be treated by nature. Furthermore, there also five types of green business in Indonesia. The types of green business are reported in Table 2. The green company have implementing one of the types. Responsible waste means the company managing the wrapping of their product, so they have more responsibility. If the company cannot responsible the waste, they can maintain their resources of the product such as for mining company reclamation, they must restore environmental functions, or for mineral water company, they must maintain the forest as the source of their product. In the other hand, the environmental service business is important too such as eco-tourism and company’s waste management. For the company who wants to have a high value, they can choose bio-resource based business such as herb, herbal medicine, cosmetics with natural ingredients or developing a biodiversity. The holistic approach for green business is applying pro-growth, pro job, pro poor, and pro-environment in every aspect.

Types of Green Business	
Responsible waste	Applying recycles Extending the chain and applying a variety of material utilization Manage waste and dispose of after meeting the safety level
Pay for the environmental and ecosystem services used	Maintain the environment's ability to produce sustainable resources.
Environmental service business	Eco-tourism Waste management: biofertilizer, bioenergy
Bio-resource based business	Biodiversity utilization industry: Herb Herbal medicine Cosmetics -nature-based Development of new materials from biodiversity
Holistic approach	Apply: pro-growth, pro job, pro poor and pro-environment (Profit, People and Planet) in every aspect (business and linkages, office management and employee.

Table 2: Types of Green Business in Indonesia

(Source: Deputy of Natural Resources-Environment, Ministry of National Development Planning/BAPPENAS, 2012)

Indonesia is a rich country for its natural resources to produce green product. Unfortunately, the number of green products made in Indonesia especially in fashion and craft is not enough to spread the love for nature. In the process of production, there are many obstacles to create a product.

D. Benchmarking Analysis

After reviewing the literature, a benchmarking analysis involves looking at the company that influence creative business. The information will used to identify where the owner brand strengths and minimize the weaknesses. The analyzing part is coming from the benchmarking in the eco business who already has a brand awareness and responsible with their product. Three benchmarking business in this section are Aesthetic Fabric, Terampil Ecoprint and Cinta Bumi Artisan. The brief history of them, vision and mission, product development and creative marketing will be explained.

a) Aesthetic Fabric

Aesthetic Fabric is a brand fashion and craft using eco-print and natural dyeing. This brand established in 2016 on their Instagram namely @aest.fabric. The owner of the company is a female called Ella Trimurti. She is a fashion designer, so she always made her own fabric using eco-print as her new collection. She produced many kinds of ready-to-wear collection such as dress, shirt, and the mask. The brand not only produce and sell the product but also having some social interaction like workshop and fashion show.

b) Terampil Ecoprint

Terampil Ecoprint is a brand fashion and craft using eco-print pattern. The brand is a sub-company of Sepatokimin which is a community organization platform to develop the villages community established in 2019. Sepatokimin is an initiative project of a group

of young Indonesian designers to support friends of ex-leprosy patients in Singkawang, West Kalimantan. The name of this project is taken from the figure of Pak Tokimin, a prosthetic technician at the Alverno Leprosy Hospital in Singkawang, who inspires us with his relentless passion to help those around him. In the beginning of 2021, Terampil Ecoprint build their own platform in Instagram with name @terampil.ecoprint.

c) Cinta Bumi Artisan

Cinta Bumi Artisan is a brand using eco-print fabric combined with other technique such as tie dye and batik established 2015. They are a small enterprise with a small team of inspired people with the Instagram name @cintabumiartisans. They started the company in the small studio which is basically a 56-sqm space on the ground floor of our house in Ubud, Bali, Indonesia. The company location in Bali is one of the strengths that the brand has. The geographical issue is giving them an opportunity to grow well. They also used their platform very good and aware of their marketing strategy because they already have a website page. It makes them easily to reach the customer from Indonesia and international. The three competitors are having their strengths and weaknesses. All the company's owner are women and their worked as entrepreneur in the eco business is more than one year. Even though their vision and mission are rarely the same but their experiencing different kind of process.

Some of the problem also happened in all company but not in the same cases. Table 3. is shown that the strengths and the weaknesses of the competitor are the same and if Saga Official can approach the strategy to minimize the weaknesses and maximize the strengths it will be good for the eco creative industry in Indonesia.

Competitor Brand	Strengths	Weaknesses
Aesthetic Fabric	Human resources, Design	Digital marketing, Location
Terampil Eco-print	Supporting community, Human resources	Digital marketing, Location
Cinta Bumi Artisans	Location, Digital marketing	Human resources, Design

Table 3: Benchmarking Analysis Result

(Source: Personal documentation, 2021)

E. Analysis of Business Situation

The resource-based view or RBV is a tool to find the resources key performance of the company. This model resulting the recommendation to emphasize the resources and capabilities in formulating creative strategy. The following tools after doing the RBV is having VRIO analysis. The RBV relies on the tangible and intangible resources that are must be heterogeneous and immobile. The tools to support the RBV analysis is VRIO framework for strategic management. The tools to make sure the value, rarity, imitability, and organization of the company's resources. Saga Official VRIO is starting from Value to the Organization questions.

- Is the resource valuable? (Value)
- Is the resource rare? (Rarity)
- Is the resource costly to imitate? (Imitability)
- Is the company organized to capture value? (Organization)

In the external analysis, the business using PESTLE analysis involves identifying the political, economic, socio-cultural, technological, legal, and environmental influences of an organization or policy in the past, and how they might do so in future. It is an analytical tool available to companies to determine how external factors influence their operations and make them more competitive in the market. This method looks at the factors in a nation or marketplace and examines how those factors affect the consumer. In strategic management, this type of analysis is used to identify, track and assess the changes that will occur in these environments and the underlying factors and the severity with which they affect it (Mihailova, 2020).

- In the industry scale, the porter five forces are the model that shape every industry. There are five forces that represent the key sources, they are competitive rivalry, supplier power, buyer power, threat of substitution, and threat of new entry.
- Competition in the industry
- Power supplier
- Power of customers
- Threat of substitute products
- Potential of new entrants into the industry

The porter five forces analysis help the owner to make a decision on the industry scale. From the analysis, the resources that still need to find is the timeline schedule for monitoring

organization, the supplier for the organic material that having a near distance with the place of the brand production, and also the branding team to make the value of the product is deliver to the customers.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research is finding by elaborating the answer from the questions in the form interview to the competitor of the business. The in-depth interview is targeting the women entrepreneurs in the eco print industry by finding their creative strategy. Each of case are produce different result and unique strategy. Then, the result is used in the business solution analysis as the primary data to process the creative strategy for women entrepreneur. The main focused in this research methodology conducted in this final project was to define creative strategy for women entrepreneurship in product development and branding, specifically for improving eco businesses in Indonesia. To answer the research questions, researcher needs to use a relevant research methodology. The methodology is descriptive, which consist of a descriptive analysis to elaborate the strategy of creative from the eco business perspective. The research was conducted based on theoretical foundation using literature study, and In-Depth Interview with structured interviews based on their degree of formality.

The research conducted was aim towards a creative strategy for new product launch and branding. The qualitative research by interview is conducted on 3 expert businesses women CEOs as the primary data, covering their current situation and the process of creative thinking in their company. The sample is selected based on criteria, i.e., produce creative product, different background, ages, and gender.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The researcher needs their experiences story of applying the strategy business from the different perspective in creativity. The topic of assessment is coming from the objective of the research and the interview question is formulated from the research question. The results from the three brands are different referring to the topic of the questions like written in the Table 4.

No.	Topic	The conclusion from Sample Survey Brands		
		Mbak Hastin from Kaine Ecoprint	Ibu Sari from Dangdaunan Ecoprint	Mas Febri from Ecoprinting
1.	Entrepreneurship	The craft industry in Indonesia has long been a source of income for most people, the environmental values become the main spirit to become an entrepreneur in this field.	Entrepreneurship is more like a collaborator action between the people who has the same vision and mission to produce a good product. The collaboration is her main action in developing the business, that is the reason why she has many partners.	The interpretation of entrepreneurship from Mas Febri is the same with Mbak Hastin and Bu Sari. The motive to be entrepreneur is coming from the willingness to produce his own product and sell it to the market.
2.	Women Entrepreneurship	Female entrepreneurs are strong and admirable. Her expertise is to make products with a personal touch so that each product has its own "life" and distinctiveness.	As a women entrepreneur in the Eco print industry, she has a good capability in building strong relation with her partners, she optimistic to handle the business with collaboration concept.	While he also argued that processing the Eco print product is suitable for the women especially for 'ibu-ibu' in the village. Even though he thinks like that but he still having high interest in Eco print pattern, and the technique is slowly getting attention from the market in Indonesia.
3.	Creative Strategy	Branding, production, and marketing are still done alone, therefore it needs development in the branding and marketing section. Background in fine art helps me be more exploratory in the manufacture of products.	Bu Sari is superior in the entrepreneurial side, but she finds difficulties to applying the creative strategy in branding and marketing her product. Until now she only focused on production and collaboration.	In the creative strategy, he is confident in his media promotion and the number of followers in the platform Instagram is good. He is aware that his lack is in producing new product, so he still wants to learn about new product development strategy.
4.	Eco Product	Eco products are products that are not only a commodity that benefits humans but are also good for nature. There is a value of usefulness and looking for opportunities to be creative without sacrificing the balance of nature.	The business is focus on the campaign of 'save the earth' by using the natural dyeing and she trying to educate the customer about the benefit and the excellence of the eco product especially Eco print product.	The eco product is something hard to produce because it is hard to find the right material and the process is very complicated.
5.	Eco print	First knew Eco print from friends in Europe then began to participate in Eco print workshop from Australia. When I found out that this product could be sell and have the market, I decided to start an Eco print business.	Specifically, she is trying to give the information about the name of the leaf that she used in every pattern of Eco print. She also active to held workshop to learn how to make the Eco print fabric. These workshops activity is aligns with the owner's mission to gain the collaboration between the people who also concern in the Eco print industry.	The Eco print is example of the simple and variative eco product because it can made by request and very flexible in the process. He believes that Eco print will bring good impact to the society and the environment.

Table 4: The Interview Results on The Three Owner Brands Sample

(Source: Personal documentation, 2021)

The first brand approached by the author is Kaine Ecoprint. The owner's name is Mbak Hastin and she was a batik teacher before deciding to be a women entrepreneur in ecoprint product. Entrepreneurship is her choices since 2017 after she encourage herself to build a brand by her own experience as a batik teacher. The women prowess is her highlight in the in-depth interview. She pointed that female or women entrepreneur has strong and admirable characters. Those characters are the main factor to make the women success as an entrepreneur because they have to face many obstacles in the process of building the business. The process is from branding to marketing the product, Mbak Hastin said that she finds difficulties in branding her product. The product is ready but her skills in the branding area is not enough to make her product awareness more exist. While she still believes that eco product is having big market and also there are many values from developing eco product especially ecoprint product for the sustainability of nature.

The second brand that the author approached after Kaine Ecoprint is Dangdaunan Ecoprint which located in Bogor, Jawa Barat. The owner of Dangdaunan Ecoprint is Bu Sari who she always said that it is a 'emak – emak' business. It means that this business is suitable for the mothers who want to be an entrepreneur in creative industry. Bu Sari believe that entrepreneur is a collaborator action between each other to produce a good product. The collaboration is her main vision in developing the business, that is the reason why she has many partners. As a women entrepreneur in the ecoprint industry she has a good capability in building strong relation with her partners. While on the other hand, Bu sari feels overwhelmed in organizing her creative strategy. She is lacking in the branding and marketing strategy because she only knew the new product development strategy. The business is focus on the campaign of 'save the earth' by using the natural dyeing and she trying to educate the customer about the benefit and the excellence of the eco product especially ecoprint product. Specifically, she is trying to give the information about the name of the leaf that she used in every pattern of ecoprint. She also active to held workshop to learn how to make the ecoprint fabric. These workshops activity is aligns with the owner's mission to gain the collaboration between the people who also concern in the ecoprint industry.

In the last sample, the author wants to collect the data from the business ecoprint who has male owner. The intention is fulfilled with the in-depth interview with Mas Febri from Ecoprinting. The interpretation of entrepreneurship from Mas Febri is the same with Mbak Hastin and Bu Sari. The motive to be entrepreneur is coming from the willingness to produce his own product and sell it to the market. While he also argued that processing the ecoprint product is suitable for the women especially for 'ibu-ibu' in the village. Even though he thinks like that but he still having high interest in ecoprint pattern and the technique is slowly getting attention from the market in Indonesia. In the creative strategy, he is confident in his media promotion and the number of followers in the platform Instagram is good. He is aware that his lack is in producing new product, so he still wants to learn about new product development strategy. The eco product is something hard to produce because it is hard to find the right material and the

process is very complicated. The ecoprint is example of the simple and variative eco product because it can made by request and very flexible in the process. He believes that eco print will bring good impact to the society and the environment.

V. ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS SITUATION

The RBV analysis relies on the tangible and intangible resources that are must be heterogeneous and immobile. The tangible assets of the business are equipment to make an ecoprint pattern and capital while the intangible assets in intellectual property. In the team is completed with the COO and the CMO but the weakness is that the brand reputation is still low because of the branding strategy is still on the first stage. The heterogeneous of skills that the owner and the team has is possessed the mix human resources. The resources of team giving the brand will achieve better advantage in the creative strategy.

The tools to support the RBV analysis is VRIO framework for strategic management. The tools to make sure the value, rarity, imitability, and organization of the company's resources. The brands' VRIO is starting from Value to the Organization questions.

- Is the resource valuable? (Value)

The company is having high value in the eco product and also the community development. The brand is trying to used 100% eco-friendly material as the basic fabric and natural dyeing for the coloring process. This value answering the question that the brand is competitive advantage.

- Is the resource rare? (Rarity)

The brand is producing the eco-print product that having a unique selling point (USP) from the exclusive pattern from the process of the making fabric. This product also rare in Indonesia because the women entrepreneurs who has this business is in small number. The product categorized as competitive rarity.

- Is the resource costly to imitate? (Imitability)

The brand is making the product with the different design and color from the other brand. The production is taking a long time to process and it needs time and intellectual team to make one product. The brand has a very competitive advantage.

- Is the company organized to capture value? (Organization)

The team is solid because each of person already know the job desk and it leads to the operational of the brand. The weakness of the organization is the timeline to produce and release the product. So, the schedule arrangement is proposed for the sustainability of the brand. The external analysis is PESTLE with explanation:

- Political factors (P)

Include an analysis of the general state of the country's green economy and the ratio between small, medium, and large businesses. The data of government policy in eco business and foreign trade policy or tax policy to trade the products in international market. As stated in the literature review, current government of Indonesia is more supporting the women entrepreneur. The form of support is like giving

many training for developing the product by online. The support from government does not stop there. Currently the SMESCO Indonesia, an official institution under the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs of the Republic of Indonesia, whose task is to help access marketing for small businesses is having many programs in digital platform for helping the SMEs marketing their products. The program name is SPARC which are SPARTRAC, SPARCCAMPUS, and SPARCTRADE.

- Economic factors (E)

Include an analysis of the general state of the country's economy in the Small and Medium Enterprise. The consumer behavior in Indonesia is slowly increasing. After the government change the policy in the middle of pandemic, the trade is lower than two years ago before the pandemic happened. Fortunately, recently the condition is slowly better, and the government take a decision to open the central of economics step by step. The entrepreneur who finds a difficulty to sell the product now can start to market the product again and the government provide the place and training event to support it.

- Socio-cultural factors (S)

Includes government policy and legislative changes that affect the economy, such as employment laws. Cover the study of demographic trends (age, sex, number, natural increase, birth rate, mortality, population migration), level of education and social groups among the population, cultural beliefs, and values (traditions, customs, beliefs, religion), culture), the individual needs of people (career aspiration, way of spending free time, etc.) The women empowerment and environmental issue is now more spreading than before. Many young generations more aware about the concept and the importance of those two topics. With that the consciousness of the brand which is having the value of women empowerment and environment more acceptable in this recent year.

- Technological factors (T)

Includes analysis covers innovation and innovation, technology transfer, the availability and access to patents, the attitude towards copyright of researchers, the availability and access to the services of research institutes. After the idea of creative formed, the entrepreneur now can register their brand immediately. The private training about the patent and learning about Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is more reachable today. When some company does not have the capability in technological based, there are many consultants or organizations that can help to support the work needed. Technological awareness is better in every aspect of life because the tools and the media are available almost everywhere.

- Legislative framework (L)

Includes sectorial legislation forming an institutional framework that develops into business environment. The eco business legality in Indonesia is being developed. For the material fabrication, there are already have a standard verification to state that the material is safe for the environment. Some of the fabrication company recently having those certifications. In the stage of entrepreneur who

wants to build a brand with value in environmental is quite hard to have the certification. Green Label Indonesia Certification is an environmentally friendly product certification which is expected to reduce the negative impact of the environment. The world market continues to be urged to be able to produce environmentally friendly products that in the future can create a sustainable environment. The certificate of products will add some value to the brand awareness. Certified products will be published on the official page of the Green Product Council Indonesia. The certificates to be given by the producers will be divided into three levels, namely Gold, Silver and Bronze according to the results of field verification conducted by the IAPMO Group Indonesia team.

- Environmental factors (E)

Includes environmental factors related to the applied technological solutions and policies in order preserve the potential of the ecological resource. This is a condition for the sustainability of economic systems. The company used an environmental issue as their concern in producing a product. The business environment is affected by natural resources of Indonesia. If the natural resources are abundantly available, their utilization will result economic development in the company's value. Then the human resources of this country are enough to build a creative environment. The number of populations of female especially is high so it is possible to rapid the economic development by the human resources. In the other hand, the developing country like Indonesia is also have an efficient and competent entrepreneur so it will support the business environment.

In the industry scale, the porter five forces are the model that shape every industry. There are five forces that represent the key sources, they are competitive rivalry, supplier power, buyer power, threat of substitution, and threat of new entry.

- Competition in the industry

The number of brand competitor is small in this year because of the pandemic happened. The workshop class to produce eco print is less happened. The impact is that the entrepreneurs in eco print business is the same with the last year. The ability of the competitor to cut the business is also small due to the different of pattern and product article that produced.

- Power supplier

The supplier of the product material is very rare because the brand used the organic material. The supplier can easily drive up the cost on inputs because there are only a few suppliers of organic material fabric and dyeing in Indonesia.

- Power of customers

The brand is new and start to release in 2021 so there are only a few customers. The brand is in the process to find new customers or markets for its product. The branding is taking important role in the process of educating the market about the eco product especially eco print product.

- Threat of substitute products
The brand product is a fashion and home décor product. The substitute is everywhere but the unique is the pattern and the material used to make it.
- Potential of new entrants into the industry
The eco print industry will growing in the future so it is the weak barriers to entry. But the new entrants may have different design and also eco value from the brand value which is 100% eco-friendly.

The porter five forces analysis help the owner to make a decision on the industry scale. From the analysis, the resources that still need to find is the timeline schedule for monitoring organization, the supplier for the organic material that having a near distance with the place of the brand production, and also the branding team to make the value of the product is deliver to the customers.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The research answers are consisting of the conclusion of the research question, the creative strategy formulation recommendation that will explained in the recommendation sub-chapter, and the implementation which explaining the action plan and the time schedule. The conclusion of the proposed brand strategy and product development are based on the research question are as follow:

- What is the creative strategy for women entrepreneur to improve the eco business in Indonesia? Eco business is having many eco products creation such as fashion and home décor product.
- How the creative strategy leads the women entrepreneur in the eco business? The steps are the guidelines for women to increase creativity of branding. The result of the research is that the women entrepreneur is superior in the process of new product development but lack of branding strategy.
- How the eco product development implemented the strategy for? The digital campaign for marketing the eco-product is start from the good process of the product development

strategy. According to the interview result, the women owner has high attention to the material and pattern of the products.

The solutions and answers to the research questions are the proposed brand strategy and product development strategy in the creative brand strategy formulation in the Figure 4 which written in the research recommendation. The form of figure about the creative strategy formulation will make it easier to execute the plan. Figure 4 showing the formulation of women entrepreneurship creativity with the creative strategy in branding and product development.

Fig. 4: Women Entrepreneur Creative Strategy Formulation

(Source: Personal documentation, 2021)

The formulation of creative strategy is starting with the women entrepreneur factor of creativity. In the literature review there are some certain mindsets as the factor of women's creativity which are resilience, confidence, attitude towards finance, ability to deal with failure, innovate, and loyal to the business. The branding strategy is including loyal to the brand, confidence, and ability to deal with failure mindset while product development is including resilience, innovation, and attitude towards finances. The research result is indicating that the most lacking control of women entrepreneur are in resilience, confidence, and ability to deal with failure. The confidence and the ability to deal with failure are in the branding strategy side while resilience in the product development strategy side, it is showing that the women entrepreneur is lacking in branding rather than in product development.

In the branding strategy, the ability to deal with failure is addressed by the improvement of brand story, the updatable information of its industry, and establishment of e-commerce business page. The updatable information is closely related with the digital branding. Recently, there are new strategy of promotion in the digital called metaverse advertisement. The brand owner can also plan the endorsement using virtual influencer and even promoting the product in the metaverse world. In the future it will be a trend and from today the women entrepreneur should concern and learn about it too. Confidence mindset is the most important but women lack in the process, the women entrepreneurs must join a workshop or exhibitions, international level is highly recommended, because the eco-business is a sexy business in the international market. The second is collaboration with the concept store, many concept store especially in the Bandung and Jakarta who accept the consignment with local brand who has high value. It should be the big opportunity for the Saga Official. The next is creating the engaging social media. This part of branding is very difficult but it worth to do. The engagement in social media is the media to deliver the value of brand by using the latest technology and the great content.

Then the loyal to the brand mindset with applying the brand pyramid, branding 101, and initiate the community empowerment is the way of the women entrepreneur to honor the customer and keep the value of the brand. On the other hand, the product development strategy also has three mindsets, the first is attitude towards finances. This mindset is including track, evaluation, and adjustment. In this part of

mindset, the women already aware. The second is innovation with NPD process, creating the product design, sample product and photo shoot, and collaboration with the community. The innovation is the best practices of women entrepreneur and must be continuing well. The last mindset but the women lack is the resilience in the entrepreneurship part, the mindset including building research and development team and getting the certification of business legality. The women lack in this part is because this is closely with the administration and bureaucracy.

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